

ECCLESIASTICAL VISION OF RT. REV. MSGR JOSEPH KUZHINJALIL

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***Abstract:** Ecclesiology is the scientific study of the Christian Church with its origin, growth, development, polity, destiny and leadership. The Universal Church has faced many issues from its very beginning and it continues even at the 21st century too. So as a student of Ecclesiology, one should be able to locate the entire characteristics of the Universal Church with the local Church or Churches in the Sui Iuris. When a special focus is given to the ecumenical ecclesiology, it becomes very clear that the Malankara Syrian Catholic Church has added a new phase of meaning to its very nature with the reunion movement. This assignment entitled “Ecclesiastical Vision of Rt. Rev. Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil” is an attempt to explore the ecclesiological vision of the founder of the DM congregation.*

Key Words: Ecclesiology, Mission, Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil

1. Introduction

Ecclesiology is the scientific study of the Christian Church with its origin, growth, development, polity, destiny and leadership. The Universal Church has faced many issues from its very beginning and it continues even at the 21st century too. So as a student of Ecclesiology, one should be able to locate the entire characteristics of the Universal Church with the local Church or Churches in the *Sui Iuris*. When a special focus is given to the ecumenical ecclesiology, it becomes very clear that the Malankara Syrian Catholic Church has added a new phase of meaning to its very nature with the reunion movement. This assignment entitled “**Ecclesiastical Vision of Rt. Rev. Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil**” is an attempt to explore the ecclesiological vision of the founder of the DM congregation. The reason behind the selection of the topic rests upon the act of opting for Malankara Mission by Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil being a member of Syro-Malabar Church. This assignment will point out few hypotheses with regard to the intention and substantiate them logically. The historical facts are slightly taken from “Monsignor Joseph Kuzhinjalil: A Profile”, a Project submitted to the Kerala University by Darly Joseph, and sources available in the internet. I am sure that this academic article will provide the descriptions with regard to the great zeal with which Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil worked for the uplifting of the people of the Southern Part of India and analyze the ecclesiological motivation by which he is inspired to join the Malankara Catholic Church.

2. Vision of Rt. Rev. Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil

2.1. Profile of Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil

The missionary spirit enkindled in the Servant of God Archbishop Mar Ivanios has been carried out successfully by Rt. Rev. Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil, the founding father of the congregation *Daughters of Mary*. Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil was born on 24th May, 1903 at Pravithanam and baptized in the same year (29th of May). He belonged to Changanassery Arch diocese and later when the diocese of Palai was installed he belonged to Palai. His parents were Mr. Kurivila and Ms Mariamma. He joined Archbishop Mar Ivanios in 1934 and initiated his missionary activities in the regions of Trivandrum and Marthandam immediately after the priestly ordination in 17th December, 1933. His missionary activities encouraged him to establish a congregation for women to facilitate the missionary activities of the Church. Therefore DM Congregation was officially inaugurated on 8th May 1938. He became Monsignor on 23rd January, 1978. As St Paul said, it is true to say that he ran his race well and gained the eternal glory on 23rd August, 1983. The following are the mission stations where he has done his missions: Marthandam, Kattachivila, Kanchiyode, Attoor, Chellamkonam, Amblikonam, Kulathoor, Kulapuram, Panachamood, Unnamalakada, Soosaipooruum and Azhakiyamandapam. It is true to say that the present Eparchy of Marthandam owed a lot to Msgr. Joseph Kuzhinjalil.

2.2. An Unexpected Deviation

It is clear from the dissertation of Darly Joseph that Msgr Joseph was carrying the joy of mission from the very early years of his formation. In other words he was ardent in spirit to bring the Cross so as to witness Christ. This missionary zeal brought him to the Malankara Catholic Church. "Desiring to extend his service to the reunited Malankara Church Fr Joseph Kuzhinjalil wrote letters to Mar Ivanios, the Archbishop of Trivandrum, expressing his desire to serve the newly formed diocese for some years. The bishop wholeheartedly invited him to Trivandrum."¹ The providence of God was with the Malankara Catholic Church from its very beginning. The Church began to increase in number. With the blessing of Archbishop Mar Ivanios, Rt. Rev. Msgr. Joseph Kuzhinjalil founded the missionary congregation of the Daughters of Mary in 1938 at Marthandom in Kanyakumari District. Through the great zeal of these missionaries, the mission of the Syro-Malankara Catholic Church spread to the southern regions of Kerala and Tamil Nadu.²

¹ Darly Joseph,44. ² <https://www.daughtersofmarysj.org>

3. Conclusion

From the given short description, I am sure that the missionary zeal of Rt. Rev. Msgr. Joseph Kuzhinjalil is made clear. What I am going to do here is to specify the ecclesiological vision here in the concluding session. The Church, the mystical body of Christ consists of diversity and all the diversity is united by focusing towards the heavenly Jerusalem with Christ, through Christ and above all in Christ. Therefore it is true to say that Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil succeeded in transcending what limits him to think particularly. He himself has taken the decision to work in the Malankara Catholic Church. Without any intension of personal gain he worked in the Malankara Church, sorry better to say CATHOLIC CHURCH. He wants to communicate the message of the broadness of mission through his life. Because when Malankara Catholic Church was blessed with the benevolent services of Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil, it was to the CATHOLIC CHURCH. The early CHURCH had the same spirit of Oneness. Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil welcomes the entire Church to go back to the roots, because all roots are directed toward a single end-CHRIST. He was ardent in spirit in serving the mystical body of Christ. That is why he worked hard to uplift the marginalized and gave proper guidance to the people of God. The term Ecclesiology means a science which may treat of the proper construction and operations of the Church, or Communion, or Society of

Christians. The ecclesiastical vision of Msgr Joseph Kuzhinjalil is encapsulated in the primary mission of bringing Good News to the poor and neglected, and concentrating families for their integrated development as well as to announce the Gospel of Christ to the end of the world.

4. Bibliography

<https://www.daughtersofmarysj.org> .

Joseph, Darly. "Monsignor Joseph Kuzhinjalil: A Profile."